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THE DEVELOPMENT OF SYNTACTIC ANALYZER ALGORITHM FOR THE UZBEK LANGUAGE

Annotation

This articles shows some linguistic approach and algorithms sequences syntactic attitudes of word combination in simple sentences in Uzbek. We testes our claim that rule based (grammar based) on syntactic word combinations between nominal and verbal class of the words. Applying this approach offered in the paper that there were higher outcome to evaluate POS models in the scope of simple sentences.

Keywords: Uzbek language, parsing, grammar based approach, Uzbek electronic corpus, computational linguistics.

Introduction. Dependency analysis methods for syntactic parsing have become well known in natural language processing in recent years. Dependency analysis is used to as a term since the nineteenth century by Lucière Tesnière’s Dependency Grammar [1]. According to this reference, the grammatical theory sentence comprises by two parts whose distinguishes between linear and structure composition. Linear linking words could be easily apprehended due to one-dimensional phase. Hence, the sequential structural connection of the sentence elements is hidden because of multi-dimensional aspect. Tesnière [1] uses stemma for vertical and horizontal relations of parts of speech which signify graphically. In this case predicate plays significant role within hierarchical level of the elements in the sentence due to governing the subject with other complements. Moreover, connection, junction and transference are basis of syntactical relations in the sentence.

Overall, two methods are applicable as approach in natural language processing: grammar-based methods (“deep”) and statistical approaches (“shallow”) [2]. In this case, dependency tee [3] is consideredas closer to semantic relations directly of components of sentence by doing beneficial outcome in NLP investigations. However, Uzbek language as an agglutinative language free component order in the sentence that can be expended as length as possible.

In this article we outlined general approaches for parser of Turkic languages by analyzing comparatively methodological aspects in section 2. Section 3 gives information a very brief introduction to Uzbek morphology and syntax and discusses the representation of morphological information and syntactic dependency relations. In section 4 we implemented applying grammar based approach by own algorithm of parsing. Given overall conclusion and further discussion in section 5.

Related works. In recent years, various approaches proposed to investigate Turkic languages parser in accordance with data collection and data analysis. The results so far primarily come from investigations developed for Turkig languages in various types of parsing methods. A related references parsing for English showed that some of the parsing relied on constituency-based representations, partly influenced by the availability of data resources such as the Penn Treebank [4].

G. Eryigit et al[4] measured two types of parser regarding to the way of solution. One is statistical parser based on probabilistic model and classier based parser. According to this research by applying Turkish treebank it has done the following implementaion: two naive parsers, which link a dependent to an IG in the next word, and one rule-based parser. Then data-driven parsers in the subsequent sections: a statistical parser using a conditional probabilistic model (from now on referred to as the probabilistic parser) and a deterministic classifier-based parser using discriminative learning (from now on referred to as the classifier-based parser).

Our previous research we applied Turkish model to analyze the texts for CoNLLU format, hence there have been the some distinction between Turkish and Uzbek structures [5].

As agreed some studies, parsing for Turkish based on the constraints in the ontology proposed by Murat Temizsoy and Ilyas Cicekli. According to this, morphological marks indicate semantic properties as well. Finding the propositional structure of the input utterance without constructing a deep syntactic tree instead it utilizes a weak interaction between syntax and semantics [6].

Moreover BOUN Treebank for Turkish applied UD main tag set and the previous conventions of Turkish annotation schemes for the most part. At the end created BoAT, a new annotation tool specifically designed for dependency parsing. BoAT is a desktop annotation tool which is specifically designed for CoNLL-U files [7].

Nivre et al. presented in his study that tokens collected and analyzed left to right to obtain the result of the rule based parser which developed version of deterministic parsing algorithm [8].

Uzbek language has rich morphological combination of the lexeme. While an inflection a number of languages, namely English – follows SVO [subject-verb-object]syntactic order, the Uzbek language follows SOV [subject-object-verb] order. It is known that sentence is consequences of words which syntactically and semantically bonding each other. The important conception of dependency is based on the notion that the syntactic structure of a sentence consists of binary and asymmetricly vertical relations between the words of the sentence. Though morphological features play important role

in syntax not every time is proper to find out the functions of the constituencies.

Our approach is relied on grammar based approach and target tokens include following linguistic features lexicon (LEX), part of speech (POS), inflections of the words (IW), features and functions of syntactic relations each words (SR).

An significant concern in our point of view is to what extent our models and algorithms are tailored to properties specific purpose as methodological aspect to improve language models based on grammar features. This issue is particularly pertinent for further data-driven approaches in NLP sphere in order to implement for syntactic analysis which is portability to applications of computational linguistics.

Morphotactic structures of Uzbek language

In this section, we focus on morphotactic structures of Uzbek language due to the syntactic role of words depends on morphological forms.

Here we can cite one example to represent this model of the word in Uzbek comparing with English:

Keltirilmaganligidanmi?=>

{kel+tir+il+ma+ganligi+dan+mi} – Because of not having been brought yet?

Considering this, a language that is characterized by rich agglutinative morphology, free constituent order, and

predominantly head-final syntactic constructions. Thus, that can be strictly differentiate word order patterns between inflected and agglutinative languages. Uzbek is an agglutinative language with a predominant Subject+Object+Verb word order, although scrambling is common, especially in spoken form. Written Uzbek language uses the Latin and Cyrillic alphabet in Uzbekistan. Structure of syntactic analyzer has three main parts: stemming, morphological analyzing and syntactic analyzing. All three parts connected to each other. Thus, there should be full information morphological word forms so that mediate syntactic functions each constituent in the text.

Stemming process. In stemming process, the main objective is to be input from user and separate each word by space then save it to array. Then each word will be compared to database root words using string similarity approach. In this approach, each input word compared letter by letter by with database root words. For example, let us say user entered vatanim, maktabning, insonlar, o‘qiyapti.

Database root words [vatan, maktabning, insonlar]. Stemming process takes each input word then compared them with database root word if input word match root database root word stemming process removes suffixes then displays remaining part of the word as a stem of the input word.

Input words	Database of token	Stem word
vatanim	Vatan+im	Vatan
maktablarning	Maktab+lar+ning	Maktab
Insonlardanmi	inson +lar+dan+mi	inson
o‘qiyapti	o‘qi+yapti	o‘qi

Morphological analyzer

Algorithm has stem form of the input word in stemming process [9, 10, 11]. In this process is morphological analyzer process that algorithm takes this list of stem words then identifies their suffixes and saves them to a suffix array. Morphological analyzer process analyzes each suffixes and identifies each stems word form (NOUN, VERB, ADJECTIVE, PRONOUN, and NUMERAL).

Input words	Database root words	Stem word	suffixes	Word class
Vatanim	Vatan	Vatan	Im	NOUN
Maktabning	Maktab	Maktab	Ning	NOUN
Insonlar	Inson	Inson	Lar	NOUN
o‘qiyati	o‘qi	o‘qi	Yapti	VERB

Syntactic analyzer

Syntactic analyzer process that identifies sentence’s Subject and VERB. In order to achieve this process, algorithm will apply each sentence’s word classes and its suffixes to a given model (word class and suffixes identified in stemming and morphological processes). It is important to state that word’s location in sentence has significant importance. Because VERB is very central to identify correlation of POS. Then depending on the VERB, algorithm will identify the SUBJECT. VERBs normally located last word of the sentence. Then VERB words normally have suffixes with that states sentence’s tense or it can state that whether sentence has PRONOUNS. For example, men (I, me), siz(you), biz (we), ular (they).

Let’s say user entered following sentence: Men maktabga bordim.

In Uzbek [OV] is available core model for any kind of type of sentences even there are nominal either verbal. Here we can see different types of word combinations in this case:

Correlation	OV in Uzbek	Example
Adposition type	Postpositions	Sen uchun keldim – I came for you.
Order of noun and genitive	genitive before noun	Onamning xatini o‘qidim – I read my mother’s letter.
Order of adjective and standard of comparison	standard before adjective	Ko‘rganlarim ichida eng chiroylisi shu edi. – this is the most beautiful things which I have ever seen.
Order of verb and adpositional phrase	adpositional phrase before verb	Ertaga samalyot orqali uchaman. – Tomorrow I fly by airplane.
Order of verb and manner adverb	manner adverb before verb	U juda tez yugura oladi. – He can run very fast.
Order of copula and predicative	predicate before copula	Men ertaga kelishim mumkin. – I may come tomorrow.

Order of auxiliary verb and content verb	content verb before auxiliary	Buni yaxshilab o'ylab ko'rishing lozim. – You have to think over.
Place of adverbial subordinator in clause	clause-final subordinators	Kelishing bilanoq menga qo'ng'iroq qil. – As soon as you arrive, give me a call.

After having general grammar features it can ease to comprehend the process of attitudes of POS in the text.

Stemming process

Input word	Stem word
Men	Men
Maktabga	Maktab
Bordim	bor

Morphological process

Input word	Stem word	Suffixes	Word class
men	men	none	PRONOUN
maktabga	maktab	ga	NOUN
bordim	bor	dim	VERB

Syntactic process

Input word	Stem word	Suffixes	Word class	Syntactic
Men	Men	NONE	PRONOUN	SUBJECT
Maktabga	Maktab	Ga	NOUN	NONE
Bordim	Bor	dim	VERB	VERB

These are formula to find Subject:

Formula for identifying Subject
If first word in sentence starts with pronoun (Men, Sen, Biz, Ular)

If sentence does not start with pronouns then algorithm goes second condition formula:

Formula for identifying Subject (two words as a Subject) If sentence has following combination:	Example
Noun+Noun	(temir uskuna)
Adjective+Noun	(qulay imkoniyat)
Pronoun+Noun	(hamma ishtirokchilar)
Number+Noun	(birinchi kun)
Gerund+Noun	(o'qiyotgan qiz)
Infinitive+Noun	(nishonlash kuni)
Adverb+Noun	(sekin harakat)
Noun+dagi(suffix)+Noun	(devordagi rasm)
infinitive+dagi(suffix)+Noun	(o'qishdagi intizom)
Adjective+dagi(suffix)+Noun	(qizildagi joziba)
Noun+dagi(suffix)+Adjective	(sinfidagi a'lochi)
Adjective+Number	(mo`jizaviy yetti)
Noun+dagi(suffix)+Number	(rasmdagi bir)
Adjective+Infinitive	(qulay joylashish)
Adverb+infinitive	(tez yeyish)

Formula for identifying Subject (three words as a Subject) If sentence has following combination:	example
Infinitive+(suffix)->dagi+Noun	ishlashdagi g'ayrat
Adverb+(suffix)->dagi+Noun	yuqoridagi qavat
Noun{ni, ga, da, dan}+Gerund+Noun	maktabga ketayotgan qiz
Adverb+Gerund+Noun	tez kelgan lahza
Noun+(suffix)->day dek)+Adjective	oyday oppoq

These are formulas to find Verb:

Formula for identifying Verb (two words as a Verb) If sentence has following combination:	Example
Adjective+Verb	yaxshi o'qimoq

Adverb+Verb	astoydil o‘qimoq
Gerund+Verb	kulib gapirmoq
Noun+(suffix)->ga+Verb	maktabga bormoq
Noun+(suffix)->ga+Infinitive	daftarga yozmoq
Noun Pronoun+(suffix)->dan+Verb	universitetdan qaytmoq
Noun Pronoun +(suffix)->ni+Verb	hikoyani o‘qimoq
Noun +(suffix)->ni+ravishdosh	ishni bajarib
Noun+(suffix)->da+Verb	maktabda o‘qimoq
Noun+(suffix)->da+Gerund	osmonda uchib kelayotgan

Algorithm for syntactic analyzer

Pseudo code for the syntactic analyzer algorithm

<pre> Input -> Tokenize(input); If TokenizeValidate(input) then return input; ===== for each Word in Words do if Input Match with DB stem then stem-> extractStem(input); else return null; ===== for each Word in Suffixes do if input Have suffix then stem-> extractSuffix(input); else return null; ===== for each Word in Wordclass do if input match with DB stem wordClass-> identifyWordClass(input); else return null; ===== for each Word in identifyWordClass do if word match with Subject formalu then subject-> identifySubject(input); else return null; ===== for each Word in identifyWordClass do if word match with Verb formalu then subject-> identifyVerb(input); else return null; ===== if (input not match DB stem && input have no prefix && input have no suffix) then return invalidWord(input); </pre>

Implementation

Syntactic analyzer tool implemented using Python Django framework and JavaScript scripts with the MySQL database. Web application is easy to access and easy to use for users. To test Syntactic analyzer simply visit <https://uzbeklinganalysis.uz/stem/syntactic> web page and type a word you want to analyze then click ‘Analyze’ button (refer to Fig 4).

Let’s test syntactic analyzer tool. Let’s say we have following three sentences.

Uzbek	English
Siz maqola yozing	You write article
Men maktabga bordim	I went to school
Biz ertalab yugurdik	We jogged in the morning

Textni Kiriting
siz maqola yozin
Analyze
Syntactic
siz(Ega) yozin(Kesim)

Fig. test 1

Textni Kiriting
men maktabga bordim
Analyze
Syntactic
men (Ega) bordim(Kesim)

Fig. test 2

Textni Kiriting
biz ertalab yugurdik
Analyze
Syntactic
biz(Ega) yugurdik(Kesim)yugurdik(Kesim)

Fig. test 3

Conclusion. As we mentioned in the article, the experiments carried out based on grammar approach as initial process of parsing. What we presented syntactic analyzer it could be one applicable tool as an open-source syntactic analyzer for the Uzbek language in NLP. Syntactic analyzer provides an interactive query interface through its website. Syntactic analyzer has a manually crafted lexicon, to reduce the number of redundant analyses. Manual configuration is an ongoing process and we modify the lexicon by inspecting the results of analyses. To the best of our knowledge, after having higher ration accuracy parsing then we can use it as a tool by automatic analysis of the Uzbek text.

As a further development, we are planning to provide an interactive tool to generate semantic analyses for Uzbek language.

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